

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

ALASH AND BASHKIR MOVEMENTS: HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT, COMMON INTERESTS, AND DISTINCTIVE FEATURES

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Abstract

The article examines the historical development of the Alash and Bashkir movements, highlighting their similarities and differences. Both movements were national liberation struggles, aiming for the political independence of their peoples. They focused on improving education to preserve their languages and cultures, addressing economic issues caused by imperial reforms, and striving for social and economic reforms. Despite these common goals, the movements differed in their approaches: Alash Orda primarily advocated for peaceful political struggle, while the Bashkirs also engaged in armed resistance.

Keywords National movements, Bashkirs, Kazakhs, National awakening.

Acknowledgments

The work was carried out with the financial support of the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan, within the framework of grant funding for the project "The History of Islamism, Turkism and Alash Movements: the Dialogue of Traditions and the Features of the Formation of National Identity" (IRN AP 23484987).

As history shows, at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, global empires experienced a period of political instability and transformation. The Kazakh steppe, which was part of the Russian Empire, was not exempt from these changes. They manifested in geopolitical, economic, social, cultural, and other spheres. Today, it can be stated that a substantial historiographical body has been formed on this topic, comprising the works of both domestic and foreign scholars.

Overall, the condition of colonized peoples was largely similar, and their histories reflect the oppression of colonial policy. For instance, the reforms adopted in the Russian Empire affected the traditional way of life of the Kazakhs, altering their land ownership rights and social structure. The empire's centralized economy and trade policies led to the decline of the traditional Kazakh economy. A similar situation can be observed in the history of the neighboring Bashkir people. The laws and decrees adopted in relation to the Bashkirs in 1894, 1889, and 1901 deprived them of 3 million dessiatinas of land, which, at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, led to a sharp escalation of class contradictions. This period was marked by the rise of mass peasant movements, as well as Muslim and national movements (1, pp. 156–157).

In the studies of Japanese scholars Ryosuke Ono and Tomohiko Uyama, it is noted: "During the Russian Empire, a movement for the improvement of the ethnic rights of the Kazakhs was actively developing. Similar to other Eastern peoples, this movement began after the 1905 revolution" (2, p. 129). As stated in this quote, the

First Russian Revolution of 1905 served as a catalyst for the emergence or activation of local political organizations and movements in the national peripheries, reinforcing the ideas of autonomy and national self-governance. The national policy of the Russian Empire, the difficult socio-economic conditions, and the colonial nature of the administrative system awakened the national consciousness of the local peoples and strengthened the perspective on the necessity of forming national autonomy. Based on such a political and national movement, it can be asserted that the Alash Orda government was established. Furthermore, the collapse of the empire and the political changes of that time gave new momentum to the activities of the Alash movement participants and created conditions for the realization of national goals.

Among the political national movements of the Russian Empire, alongside the Alash movement, the Bashkir movement can also be noted. Like the Alash movement, the foundation of the Bashkir movement was the desire to implement national liberation, social, economic, and political reforms. Additionally, the interconnection between these movements can be observed. Japanese scholars Ryosuke Ono and Tomohiko Uyama state: "In addition to negotiating with the Provisional Siberian Government, Alash Orda also sought to establish cooperation with the Bashkir Autonomous Government, which was striving for territorial autonomy, and with the Turkestan Autonomous Government. Initially, the Bashkirs actively supported this cooperation, and in December 1917, at the Third Bashkir Kurultai held in Orenburg, they proposed the creation of an alliance between Turkestan, Bashkortostan, and Kazakhstan (Kazakhia), and accordingly suggested that the government of this alliance join an alliance with other governments of Russia" (2, p. 132). They also add: "According to the specific leader of the Bashkir Autonomous Government, the orientalist Akhmetzaki Validi, representatives of the Bashkir, Kazakh, and Turkestan Autonomous Governments met in Semipalatinsk from July 18 to 21, 1918, and then at the end of

August and early September in Samara and other cities. At these meetings, the decision was made to create the 'Turkestan Federation' and to form a united army of Bashkirs and Kazakhs" (2, p. 133).

The goals of the two movements were not significantly different. The Alash Orda government aimed to establish the political independence of the Kazakhs of that time and create an autonomous system of governance, preserve the culture and language of the Kazakh people, implement reforms in education and the economy, as well as raise the political literacy of society. Among the founders of this movement, the Kazakh intellectuals Alihan Bukeikhan, Ahmet Baitursynuly, Mirzhakyp Dulatov, and others can be mentioned. Similarly, after the abdication of Emperor Nicholas II, leading figures of the Bashkir people, such as Z. Validi Toġan, Sh. Manatov, and S. Mryasov, proposed a model of the national state structure of Bashkortostan (3, p. 53). Like the Alash Orda government, the Bashkirs also considered the broader state interests.

When discussing the similarities between the Alash and Bashkortostan movements, the following points can be highlighted: 1) both movements were national liberation movements, as they fought for the national independence of their peoples; 2) both movements aimed to improve the education system in order to preserve their language and culture, making education and culture a priority in their views; 3) both movements sought to address the issues of agriculture and land, which had declined due to imperial reforms, and to improve the economic conditions of the people, meaning both movements focused on socio-economic reforms; 4) resistance to the central authority of the Russian Empire and attempts to create an autonomous governance system manifested as opposition to the central and colonial authorities.

Regarding their differences, the following points can be noted: 1) politically, Alash Orda mainly supported peaceful political struggle, whereas the Bashkirs also resorted to armed struggle; 2) in relation to the Bolshevik government, Alash Orda attempted to cooperate

with the Soviet authorities but expressed resistance to Bolshevik policies, whereas the Bashkirs reached a compromise with the Soviet government, managing to temporarily preserve national autonomy; 3) during the Civil War, the Bashkir movement formed an alliance with the Red Army, while the supporters of Alash Orda, due to the complex political situation, temporarily established contact with the White Guards. The participation of Alash Orda forces in battles against the Red Army is discussed in the works of researchers D. Amanzholova and B. Äbdıghalıuly (4, p. 12).

In conclusion, the history of the Alash and Bashkortostan movements still requires in-depth research, which will continue in future works. Both movements became a vivid manifestation of the period of national awakening, reflecting the people's desire to preserve their identity, develop culture and the social sphere, as well as to achieve political independence. Historically, the ideas and goals of these movements, as we see, remain relevant even today.

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